

Zinc(II) Complexes with 2-Aminopyridine and 4-Aminoantipyridine

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As a part of a series of investigations on complexes of metals containing symmetrical non-bonding shells viz., d^0, d^5 and d^{10} , we reported¹ earlier several zinc (II) complexes with substituted pyridines. In this communication, we report some more complexes by reacting zinc salts, ZnX_2 where X is Cl^- , Br^- , I^- NO_3^- and ClO_4^- with 2-aminopyridine and 4-aminoantipyridine.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the materials used are of pure quality. Zinc perchlorate was prepared by treating A.R. perchloric acid with excess of zinc carbonate. The ligands used are of Fluka pure grade. An ethanolic solution of zinc salt was treated (refluxed in some cases) with an ethanolic solution of ligand in stoichiometric amount. The separated compounds were suction filtered, washed with ether and dried *in vacuo*.

The purity of the isolated compounds was established by estimating the metal and the halogen by standard methods. In case of 4-aminoantipyridine complexes, the direct estimation of halogen presented difficulties. The complex was therefore subjected to alkaline fusion prior to precipitation of silver halide. In addition to metal and halogen, nitrogen was estimated in one representative compound, dichloro bis-(2-aminopyridine)

TABLE I

Analysis, M. P. and Conductance of Zinc (II) Complexes with 2-aminopyridine and 4-aminoantipyridine.

Complex	Colour and Form	M.P. °C	% Zinc		% Halogen		ΛM in (mhos)
			Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	
Dichloro bis (2-aminopyridine) Zinc (II)	Yellow crystalline	155	20.0	20.1	21.8	21.9	3.7
Dibromo bis (2-aminopyridine) Zinc (II)	Yellow crystalline	142	15.1	15.7	38.4	38.7	5.3
Dichloro bis (4-aminoantipyridine) Zinc (II)	Amorphous Pink	148	11.7	11.9	12.9	13.1	11.6
Dibromo bis (4-aminoantipyridine) Zinc (II)	Light Yellow amorphous	178	10.6	10.3	25.1	25.3	6.5
Diiodo bis (4-aminoantipyridine) Zinc (II)	White crystalline	150	8.8	8.9	34.7	35.0	39.1
Dinitrato bis (4-aminoantipyridine) Zinc (II)	White crystalline	139	11.0	10.9	47.8
Tetrakis (4-aminoantipyridine) Perchlorate Zinc (II)	White crystalline	245d	6.1	6.0	265

1. S. Guru and D. V. Ramana Rao, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1967, **44**, 594.

zinc(II) (Found: 16.7, Reqd: 17.3%). All the complexes are soluble in acetone. The perchlorate complex, however, has poor solubility, due perhaps to ionic nature. The conductance measurements were carried out in acetone medium using a Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge and a dip type cell. The relevant analytical and conductance data are recorded in table I.

The infra-red absorption spectra were recorded on Nujol mulls using a Unicam SP-200 double beam spectrophotometer and the absorption bands in the region 5000-650 cm^{-1} are reported in table II.

TABLE II

Infrared absorption bands (cm^{-1}) in Nujol mulls of Zinc(II) Complexes with 2-aminopyridine and 4-aminoantipyrine

L	L=2-aminopyridine		L	L=4-aminoantipyrine		
	ZnL ₂ Cl ₂	ZnL ₂ Br ₂		ZnL ₂ Cl ₂	ZnL ₂ Br ₂	ZnL ₂ I ₂
755s	755s	755s	718s	718s	718s	718s
			740sh	742w	742s	745s
790 s	785 s	790 vs	760 sh	—	—	—
			775 vs	790 vs	785 s	780 vs
880 w	875 w	875 w	860 w	870 w	875 vw	850 s
						875vw.
1005 s	1030 s	1030 s	942 w	950 br. w	945 br. w	940 w
	1070 s	1070 s	1000 w	1000 sh	1010 vw	—
			1040 w	1030 w	1025 w	—
			1055 w	1045 w	—	1050 br
			1090 w	1075 w	1090 w	1110 br
1170 s	1175 s	1175 s	1130 s	—	—	—
			1170 s	1175 w	1165 vw	—
1290 w	1270 s	1265 s	1208 s	—	—	—
			1240 s	—	—	—
			1282 s	—	—	—
1340 w	1345 s	1345 s	1320 s	1320 s	1340 w	1340 sh
1570 s	1570 vs	1570 s	1592 vs	1590 w	1590 w	1585 w
1615 s	1625 s	1620 sh	1645 vs	1620 s	1610 s	1620 br
	1645 vs	1645 vs				

s-sharp, vs-very sharp; w-weak; vw-very weak; sh-shoulder; br-broad.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All the compounds reported in this communication are presumably tetrahedral complexes involving the use of $4s4p^3$ hybrid bonding orbitals. The dihalo bis-(2-aminopyridine) zinc(II) complexes have low melting points and are non-electrolytes in acetone medium. They are not ionic but are covalently bonded complexes. Even on refluxing with excess (6 moles) ligand only 1:2 compound was formed. No compound could be isolated by reacting either zinc iodide or zinc perchlorate with 2-aminopyridine.

The ligand, 4-aminoantipyrine can co-ordinate to the metal by donation of a lone pair of electrons from the oxygen of the carbonyl group. It has earlier been shown² that

2. C. C. Patel, personal communication.

antipyridine is a poor donor and gets bonded to the metal through carbonyl oxygen. In course of his analytical investigations of metal complexes of antipyridine, Souchay reported³ the compounds having the formula ZnL_2X_2 where L is antipyridine and X is a halide or nitrate group. In the present studies, the stress is not on analytical aspect and further 4-aminoantipyridine has been used as a ligand but not simple antipyridine. The compounds ZnL_2X_2 and $ZnL_2(NO_3)_2$, where X is Cl^- , Br^- , I^- and L is 4-aminoantipyridine have low melting points and are non-electrolytes in acetone medium. They are presumably tetrahedral being covalently bonded to the metal. We had distinguished⁴ earlier an ionic nitrate from a coordinated nitrate group by studying I. R. spectra. In case of the present $ZnL_2(NO_3)_2$ compound, we could not rely on I.R. spectrum on account of overlapping of the numerous ligand absorption bands. However, the non-electrolytic nature of the compound is a definite evidence for the absence of an ionic nitrate group. The compound $(ZnL_4)(ClO_4)_2$ does not melt at a low temperature but decomposes at a higher temperature, 245°, indicating the presence of an ionic bond. The molar conductance value in acetone (265 mhos) also indicates a 1:2 electrolyte.

Since the ligand is not free but bonded to the metal, some of the characteristic ligand absorption bands have been modified in the complexes. Thus, in 2-aminopyridine complexes, the bands at 1005 and 1615 cm^{-1} were shifted to a higher frequency whilst the band at 1290 cm^{-1} was shifted to a lower frequency. Similarly, in 4-aminoantipyridine complexes, the band at 1645 cm^{-1} was shifted to a lower frequency. This is expected in complexes due to change in different bond orders consequent to the metal-ligand bonding. Direct M-N or M-O stretching frequencies could not be recorded since they are beyond the range of the spectrophotometer used.

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